

MULTIFACETED STRUCTURES IN ARCHITECTURE

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Annotation. The article analyzes the problems of using polyhedra and their modifications in architecture, construction and technology. Prisms, pyramids, prismatoids, Platonic and Archimedean solids, quasi-polyhedra and some figures composed on their basis, as well as polyhedral domes, umbrella shells and folds from flat fragments of the same type are considered.

Key words: polyhedra, prisms, pyramids, architecture, architectural compositions, multifaceted dome, umbrella shell.

Introduction. Currently, 75 homogeneous polyhedra, a large number of their star-shaped forms and 9 quasi-polyhedra are known. A polyhedron is a figure bounded by flat polygons. A quasi-polyhedron is a figure bounded by non-plane equal pieces of surfaces. Scientists are introducing new forms of “ruled quasipolyhedra”, which can significantly expand the capabilities of classical polyhedra [2, 4, 5].

In the scientific and technical literature there are many works on the use of analytical surfaces in the selection of forms for civil and industrial structures, industrial products, and for the configurations of various small architectural forms. For example, surfaces of revolution [3, 4] are widely used, including conical surfaces [1] and paraboloids of revolution [2], elliptic paraboloids [6, 7], and cyclic surfaces [8, 9]. Slightly less commonly used are umbrella surfaces and umbrella-type surfaces, torso surfaces [10, 11] and surfaces that are not specified analytically. Very rarely, but still used are velaroidal surfaces [12] and pseudospheres [14].

Some prominent modern architects believed that rectangular shapes and the presence of planes in the configurations of buildings give them a dull appearance and monotony. They in every possible way promoted the use of curvilinear shell forms, therefore, in 1960-2000 there were practically no serious works that analyzed the use of polyhedra in architecture or mechanical engineering, despite the fact that these figures were very widely represented in the mathematical literature [12, 13]. But in the last decade, architects, designers and builders have greatly increased interest in polyhedra and analytically undefined surfaces, similarly among mathematicians. Even the term “architecture of polyhedra” appeared. A large number of buildings were built in the form of polyhedra, folds, and complex surfaces. Apparently, the innovative shaping of long-span thin-walled shells outlined along canonical surfaces and buildings of a simple rectangular shape has exhausted itself; any new structure has become a repetition of already built analogues.

Of the polyhedra, those of greatest practical interest to architects and mechanical engineers are prisms, pyramids, prisms, regular and semi-regular convex polyhedra. Regular convex polyhedra, that is, Platonic solids, are the tetrahedron, hexahedron, octahedron, dodecahedron and icosahedron. A polyhedron is called regular if its faces are regular and equal polygons, and the polyhedral angles at the vertices are equal. If the vertices and edges of a polyhedron are on the same side of the plane of any of its faces, then the polyhedron is called convex.

Archimedean solids are semi-regular polyhedra obtained from regular ones by cutting off their vertices. There are 13 types of Archimedean solids: cuboctahedron, icosidodecahedron, truncated tetrahedron, truncated octahedron, truncated icosahedron, truncated cube, truncated dodecahedron, cuboctahedron, rhombicosidodecahedron, rhombicuboctahedron, rhombic truncated icosidodecahedron, snub cube, snub dodecahedron. In popular scientific literature there are other names for the same Archimedes bodies.

A prism is a polyhedron whose two bases are n-gons, and the remaining n side faces are parallelograms. Prisms can be triangular or quadrangular, depending on whether

the base is a triangle or a quadrangle. In addition, they are divided into straight and inclined prisms.

A pyramid is a polyhedron, the base of which is a polygon, and the remaining side faces are triangles with a common vertex.

A prisma is a polyhedron, two of whose faces (bases) lie in parallel planes, and the rest are triangles or trapezoids. Moreover, triangles have one side, and trapezoids have both bases that are sides of the bases of the prisma.

A prisma is called an antiprism if its bases are equal regular polygons, the centers of which belong to the common normal to them, but one is rotated relative to the other around the normal at an angle $\varphi = 180^\circ / n$ (n is the number of sides of the polygon).

A tetrahedron is a regular tetrahedron consisting of four equilateral and congruent triangles. The triangles are connected in threes near each vertex. A tetrahedron is a special case of a pyramid.

A hexahedron is a regular hexagon (cube) consisting of six equal squares. A cube is a special case of a prism.

An octahedron is a regular octahedron consisting of eight equilateral and equal triangles, connected by four at each vertex. An octahedron is a polyhedron composed of two quadrangular pyramids connected to each other by their square bases.

The dodecahedron is a regular dodecahedron, consisting of twelve regular and equal pentagons, connected by three near each vertex. If we take two parallel pentagons as the bases of the dodecahedron, then the remaining ten pentagons form its lateral surface.

An icosahedron is a regular twenty-sided triangle, consisting of twenty equilateral and equal triangles, connected by five at each vertex. The midpoints of the faces of the icosahedron are the vertices of the dodecahedron. A hexagon is a regular polygon. However, if you connect three hexagons at one point, you get a plane, that is, you cannot build a three-dimensional figure from identical hexagons alone. Any other regular polygons above a hexagon cannot form solids at all.

Direct prisms are the most common polyhedra in the architecture of any city. With a certain approximation, you can see polygonal prisms in the forms of approximate vertical cylindrical buildings or their fragments and in the forms of horizontal prefabricated or monolithic prismatic reinforced concrete coverings of industrial buildings.

Prismatoids include prismatoid polyhedra, antiprisms and truncated pyramids.

The prismatoid was taken as a basis when designing the external shape of some palaces. The external shape is formed by triangles and rectangles, which greatly simplifies the construction of the external thin-sheet metal shell. Prismatoids with trapezoidal faces are obtained by approximating some torso surfaces with folds. Theoretically, this issue has been resolved, but perhaps in the future there will be practical application.

Tetrahedra are used in architecture. They are often called pyramids, which is justified, since a tetrahedron is a special case of a pyramid. The capabilities of this form are demonstrated by one interesting project and one real structure.

Hexahedrons (cubes) and parallelepipeds are the main elements of the Cubist architectural style. It is believed that this style is created by minimalist forms and laconic design.

The original Cube Tube complex was built in China, the main element of which is an office building in the shape of a cube. The architects of the Sako Architects bureau, through the use of a large number of window openings of various sizes, gave the building a simple shape and a memorable look. Several hexahedrons form the National Science Museum of Thailand.

In many countries of Western and Central Europe, during excavations of settlements from the era of the Roman Empire (I-IV centuries AD), small, from 4 to 10 centimeters in diameter, hollow objects made of bronze or stone are found. Each such object has the shape of a geometrically regular polyhedron - a dodecahedron - 12 equal pentagonal sides. The dodecahedron was considered by the Pythagoreans to be a sacred figure that personified the Universe. The dodecahedron has 15 planes

of symmetry. Any of the planes of symmetry passes in each face through the top and middle of the opposite edge. He is considered a fairly famous mathematical figure. There is a monument to the dodecahedron in Belgium, in the open-air museum of mathematics and other cities around the world.

Innovative architects are breaking the stereotypical idea of the beauty of buildings, using in their projects now non-convex multifaceted bodies, all points of which lie on different sides of each face, which, according to the architects, allows them to achieve a stunning effect. A typical example is the Seattle Public Library. Architect R. Koolhaas tried to make the building as futuristic as possible. Not all residents of the city liked the broken shapes of the eleven-story building made of glass and steel mesh, and for many they simply caused indignation.

Conclusions. Escaping the routine of traditional thinking is the lot of innovators in architecture and engineering. This gives rise to prospects for the innovative design of public buildings and technical structures, which can be more artistically meaningful. It is obvious that now structures and structures designed using innovative spatial forms are considered iconic for a region, city or country. Analytically undefined surfaces created by architects according to their professional intuition and technical requirements, and core regular and semi-regular polyhedral structures are taken as innovative forms.

There are several dozen objects in the form of antiprisms and rhombicuboctahedra. The inclined prism, tetrahedron, octahedron, tetrahedron, icosahedron, truncated tetrahedron, truncated octahedron are used in isolated cases, and the remaining regular and semi-regular polyhedra are used mainly as small architectural forms or sculptural compositions. Everything else exists only in the form of concept projects.

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